

The End of a Dogma – The Substantive Amendment of the German Guideline on Vertigo in May 2026: No Recommendation for High-Dose Betahistine

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The 2025 German guideline “Vertigo in General Practice” (AWMF register number 053–018) was recently criticised in a methodological-scientific statement for its distorted presentation of evidence and for therapeutic statements without a scientific basis (Gürkov 2026).

In particular, the guideline statement that a therapeutic effect was to be expected with off-label high-dose betahistine was published by the guideline authors — detached from the actual global evidence base — without mentioning the standard reference, the BEMED study, which tested precisely this hypothesis. The BEMED study is by far the highest-quality study in this field and has excluded, with high certainty, a therapeutic effect of betahistine, both at the standard dose and at a three-fold off-label overdose (Adrion 2016).

As a consequence of this scientific criticism, this guideline has now been substantively amended in May 2026 — silently.

The statement:

“With betahistine, an effect appears to be expected only at considerably higher doses (studies on this are currently ongoing).”

has been deleted without replacement.

In the current, substantively revised version of the guideline, there is therefore no longer any mention, let alone recommendation, of off-label high-dose Betahistine. This represents a departure from the dogma, propagated over many years, of an alleged efficacy of this high-dose therapy without a corresponding evidence base. Moreover, this deletion proves that these allegedly “ongoing studies” do not exist; they were not cited anywhere in the guideline with over 380 references, neither in the old version nor in the new version.

What remains problematic, however, is that the guideline authors do not transparently disclose this clear substantive change. In the current version of the guideline (downloaded on 21 May 2026), it still states:

“Status 02/2025”. This does not correspond to the facts, because the substantive amendment was carried out and published in May 2026.

Even more serious is the statement on the title page of the AWMF guideline that only an “editorial revision” took place in May 2026. In addition, the new version contains no comparison between the old version and the amended new version. Both lead readers astray and falsely make them assume that the changes concerned only linguistic smoothing or something similar. This is incompatible with the fact that a specific substantive statement on a specific therapy was changed.

On the DEGAM website, it also states:

“published 08/2025, valid until 02/2030”, without any reference to the substantive amendment in May 2026.

Furthermore, the new version still contains an incomprehensible selection of the cited evidence. Betahistine is by far the most frequently prescribed drug in the past among all medications addressed in the guideline. Numerous and very heterogeneous primary studies and review articles exist on this topic. The internationally highest-quality primary study by far is unquestionably the BEMED study. Nevertheless, the guideline authors have continued to decide not to mention this reference study in the guideline, which at the same time lists over 380 other references, many of them concerning extremely rare diseases that are typically not primarily treated in general practice. Furthermore, for the entire topic of betahistine, only a single review article was selectively cited, although this review is known to be seriously flawed (Gürkov 2026b).

Furthermore, the first published version of the guideline made the following therapeutic statement on Ménière’s disease (hydropic ear disease):

“Betahistine dihydrochloride (up to 48 mg/day, divided into several individual doses), possibly in combination with selegiline 5 mg/day or rasagiline 1 mg/day), low level of evidence to date.”

This experimental combination therapy in the guideline for general practitioners was also criticised methodologically and scientifically by Prof. Gürkov.

Subsequently, a footnote to this sentence has now been added in the current version of the guideline:

“() Combination to date only in the context of studies.”*

This guideline statement also remains highly problematic:

- 1) The question arises why a purely experimental therapy, which allegedly has so far only been used in studies, is listed at all as a therapeutic option in a guideline for general practitioners.
- 2) This statement, too, does not correspond to the actual evidence base. Quite simply, there is not a single published study on this experimental combination therapy (nor is a single study on it cited anywhere in the entire guideline); that is, the statement “low level of evidence” is simply false.

In summary, it can be stated that now, finally, after more than 15 years, the stereotypically propagated dogma of high-dose betahistine therapy is off the table. However, even in the new version of the guideline, massive methodological and substantive deficiencies remain unmistakable and urgently require correction.

References:

- Adrion C, Fischer CS, Wagner J, Gürkov R, Mansmann U, Strupp M; BEMED Study Group. Efficacy and safety of betahistine treatment in patients with Meniere’s disease: primary results of a long term, multicentre, double blind, randomised, placebo controlled, dose defining trial (BEMED trial). *BMJ*. 2016 Jan 21;352:h6816. doi: 10.1136/bmj.h6816. PMID: 26797774; PMCID: PMC4721211.
- Gürkov, R. (2026). Criticism of evidence distortion in the DEGAM/AWMF guideline “Vertigo in General Practice” 2025. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18847495>

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